

IMPORTANCE OF ARBITRATION COURTS TODAY

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ABSTRACT

Arbitration courts increase the importance of ensuring that ready-made analytical data and research on the work carried out at the level of state courts is done

In our country, democratic reforms are more strengthening of citizens and their freedom is a reliable guarantee, the law is a priority and Social justice provides a significant deal done by increasing the approach. At the present stage of liberalization of the judicial system, ¹which is an important direction of these reforms, arbitration courts have established themselves as an institution of alternative dispute resolution, which is trusted by citizens and entrepreneurs and which functions effectively.

Arbitration court - citizenship legal from relations coming outgoing conflicts, that's all, including between economic entities to the body incoming economic disputes decision maker non-governmental body. Arbitration court disputes Uzbekistan Republic laws and legality documents based on the decision makes

Arbitration court directly International in the circle application arbitration court through the made increased some in the States only arbitration court activity show, but in Uzbekistan Arbitration courts and arbitration courts separately individual disputes alternative decision to achieve method Considered

Arbitration is a dispute between the parties, an agreement depending on, a dispute in accordance with a binding decision, making one or one how many judges to be submitted to the procedure. Arbitration in choosing a party to go to court to make a decision instead of a dispute to make a private order they choose

Its main functions are as follows:

Arbitration only both to agree was just in case made to increase may In the future the contract in accordance with the disagreement surface came in the case, the parties belong to the contract arbitration court clause They entered. There is a dispute between the parties in the middle and the gift to reach an agreement through arbitration to the court can be sent. From another type of mediation, one party on a bilateral basis, respectively, arbitration from the court cannot publicly declare

rules , in the opinion of the parties, the arbitration court decision to execute without delay agree that they receive International awards national Courts to the New York Convention in

¹ Uzbekistan Arbitration courts association chairman, arbitration judge Khamza Makhmudov

More: <https://kknews.uz/oz/71189.html>

accordance with the done increases until they are very limited only in cases of emptiness to do permission from the ladies. from 165 more countries than this Agreement is a party to.²

Arbitration of courts has a useful side. This is its importance. How does the effect show? The state of the courts behind can leave such as to the questions as shown below comparisons through answering we get can

1. The biggest difference is that arbitration in court matters is the speed with which a decision will be made. Arbitration in court is only one from the stage consists of this is another Courts such as appeal, cassation, control cases there are no.

The American Lawyers Association stated that the arbitration work from the beginning of the final decision to the release was an average time of approximately Seven months to organize does, citizenship works in accordance with the average time until the court how busy it is from 23 to 30 months depending on continue enough

2. Arbitration to deal with the parties to the criminal and administrative liability was not weighed;

3. Arbitration court process for the costs of arbitration court judge payment (claim amount, arbitration examination and costs depending on) and lawyer payments with a limited limit. Also you arbitrate for the place The price you pay may need

The state of the court process for the costs of the lawyer fees in court was Requests and questions, documents checked and court costs included, they may be very high

4. Arbitration court is the main purpose of the parties to the agreement begins and the parties in the middle of the optional cooperation to the body brings;

5. Arbitration court for economic and citizenship works, seeing the outcome, decide will be done. But citizenship in the courts is only visible to citizens regarding disputes; economics in the courts will only be visible to legal entities regarding economic disputes;

6. Arbitration discussion confidentiality » Arbitration courts on the law with Guaranteed:

" Arbitration to judge arbitration discussion during the course of which he himself knows the existence of the remaining information arbitration discussion of the parties or their legal successors without your consent is disclosed to do this correctly is not. Arbitration judge arbitration discussion during he himself knows the existence of the remaining data about the witness as a question needs to be made possible it is not "³ such as rules certain .

7. Arbitration courts payment amount Citizenship or economic affairs in accordance with in court payment upon presentation of the state from 50 percent of the fee does not exceed

8. The arbitration court's decision to act as a decision until the adoption made from the day beginning to rule enters;

9. Economical and citizenship works in accordance with the Courts arbitration court to certain circumstances Check or arbitration court decision to act decision content again seeing come out correctly it is not:

" Authorized court arbitration court decision to act decision emptiness do about application seeing At the exit arbitration court certain circumstances Check or arbitration court decision to act decision content again seeing exit right it is not "⁴

10. The law with guaranteed again one aspect From this consists of the arbitration court decision to act the decision optional accordingly not executed in the case, it belongs to the binding focus can In this Arbitration court optional not executed decision competent to the court the gift is made and executed sheet receive through made increased .⁵

The above shows the authorities of the parties no matter what in Uzbekistan the arbitration court is ten state in the courts than much lower.

² <https://www.wipo.int/amc/en/arbitration/what-is-arb.html>

³ "Arbitration courts". Article 28 of the law: <https://lex.uz/docs/-1072079#-1072324>

⁴ "Arbitration courts". Article 47 of the law is the first part: <https://lex.uz/docs/-1072079#-1072324>

⁵ Bakhromov K. A., ADVANTAGES OF ARBITRATION COURTS OVER STATE COURTS, 2022.:

More: <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/2982>

Uzbekistan in the Republic of Arbitration courts to organize from completion after the dispute an alternative decision to reach in the field News appears it was i.e. arbitration courts through disputes the decision to reach began It is to the court to be out of the burden to get rid of to reach in order for the President of June 17, 2020 "Conflicts" alternative solution to achieve mechanisms for more improvement of measures about." resolution of disputes before the court seeing the only way out system creation, mediation , arbitration courts and international arbitration have a role to radically increase their citizens and entrepreneurs in the activities of appearing to be a dispute resolution in achieving great power to be determined.

But now the arbitration courts have heard and known to citizens or entrepreneurs the weighty Arbitration of the courts, the importance of knowing for arbitration in the courts to take cases for the amount of look if we give up all of them becomes clear.

For example , 15 Arbitration courts established at the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional branches.

2007-2017 saw a total of 10,446 cases, claiming the amount is 503.5 billion dollars. 54.2 million soums. US dollars , 195.1 thousand Euros organized in 2017 Arbitration courts 2465 works visible to be a claim amount 114.2 billion soums, 5.4 million US dollars. organize did This in 2016 visible cases per number compared to 1204 There are many.⁶

In the period from 2007 to 2017, that is, after 10 years, there are no 10,446 cases visible from this except this visible case 15 arbitration court through the decision made This compares in order to State Economical courts the first in the quarter saw work look let's quit Only in 2023 year 85,581 jobs in the first quarter economic Courts to saw ⁷Of course, this is economic Courts saw cases all in the republic visible cases It is considered But after 10 years visible cases after 3 months visible cases between the difference is very high From this it seems Uzbekistan in the republic Arbitration courts importance still very low.

Brief summary of the execution to say If yes, then the arbitration courts of Uzbekistan in the republic are a new institution, the existence of it to organize a small opportunity made it was. Arbitration of the court reputation to increase and its importance to strengthen about today on that day to a significant case done has increased that's all in accordance with the arbitration of the courts above seeing came out analytical data for him development and the importance of raising to use the guide existence service to do and scientists new explore the interval more extended from the movement we hope

Used books:

1. Uzbekistan Arbitration courts association chairman, arbitration Judge Hamza Makhmudov
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2. " Arbitration courts". Article 28 of the law : <https://lex.uz/docs/-1072079#-1072324>
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5. <https://www.wipo.int/amc/en/arbitration/what-is-arb.html>
6. Arbitration courts and international commerce arbitration activity Results and their development prospects discussion. Read more: <https://chamber.uz/uz/news/1774>
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⁶ Arbitration courts and international commerce arbitration activity Results and their development prospects discussion. Read more: <https://chamber.uz/uz/news/1774>

⁷ <https://stat.sud.uz/iib.html>